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EVALUATION OF MOLDING PROCESSES EFFECTS ON INTERNAL GEOMETRY OF RANDOMLY ORIENTED STRANDS

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- Randomly Oriented Strands (ROS)
- Objectives

II. Fabrication

- Sheet molding carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (SM-CTT)
- Bulk molding carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (BM-CTT)
- Free-edge charged carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (FC-CTT)

III. Internal geometry

- X-ray micro-CT
- Image processing

IV. Conclusion

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Randomly oriented strands (ROS)

Carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT), tow-based discontinuous composites (TBDCs)

Fiber volume fraction (V_f)	Over 50%
Fiber length	Around 10 to 100 millimeters
Complex molding	Suitable
Orientation	Generally transversely isotropic

Complex shape modeling [4]

[1] "TCAC_BulkMouldingCompounds". Royal TenCate Corporate EMEA. <http://www.tencate.com/>
 [2] "HexMC_User Guide". Hexcel.com. http://www.hexcel.com/Resources/UserGuides/HexMC_User%20Guide.pdf
 [3] Selezneva M, et. al. J Compos Mater, 2015. 50(20): p. 2833-2851.
 [4] LeBlanc D, et. al. Proceeding of the International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition 2014, Seattle WA, USA.

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ROS Window Frames for 787^[1]

Hybrid ROS^[2]

ROS application on automobiles (Lamborghini)^[3]

[1] "Window Frames for 787". Tulsa World. <http://www.tulsaworld.com/>

[2] "Hybrid ROS composites". M.C. Gill Composites Center, University of Southern California. CAMX 2016

[3] "Forged composites". Lamborghini. <https://www.lamborghini.com/en-en/brand/forged-composites>

Randomly oriented strands (ROS)

Heterogeneous and variability in mechanical properties

Fiber volume fraction (V_f)	Over 50%
Fiber length	Around 10 to 100 millimeters
Complex molding	Suitable
Orientation	Generally transversely isotropic

[1]

[2]

[1] Selezneva M, et. al. J Compos Mater, 2015. 50(20): p. 2833-2851.

[2] Feraboli P, et. al. J Reinf Plast Comp, 2009. 28(10): p. 1191-1214.

Randomly oriented strands (ROS)

Effect of strand morphologies on mechanical performances

Fiber volume fraction (V_f)	Over 50%
Fiber length	Around 10 to 100 millimeters
Complex molding	Suitable
Orientation	Generally transversely isotropic

[1]

[1] Yamashita S. Doctoral Thesis, Department of Systems Innovation. The University of Tokyo, 2017, Tokyo, Japan.

Randomly oriented strands (ROS)

Effect of molding processes on internal geometries

Fiber volume fraction (V_f)	Over 50%
Fiber length	Around 10 to 100 millimeters
Complex molding	Suitable
Orientation	Generally transversely isotropic

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Carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT)

ROS for Mass Production

BM (bulk molding)-CTT

SM (sheet molding)-CTT

FC (Free-edge charged)-CTT

Fiber volume fraction (V_f)	Over 50%
Fiber length	Around 10 to 100 millimeters
Complex molding	Suitable
Orientation	Generally transversely isotropic

CTT

Molding method: Randomly dispersed chopped tapes;
Compressing molding (heating and cooling)

Components: CF (TR 50S); Nylon 6 (Polyamide 6)

Prepreg sheet thickness: 44 μ m

Chopped tape length: 18mm

Chopped tape width: 5mm

Molding condition: 260°C, 5MPa, (5 min for FC-CTT)

normal prepreg (150 μ m)

UT prepreg (150 μ m)

BM-CTT

SM-CTT

FC-CTT

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X-ray observation

Sample size: 2×2×30 mm (thickness × width × length)
3D X-ray scan system: TDM1000-II from Yamato Scientific Co., Ltd.
Scanning conditions: X-ray tube voltage: 40 kV; X-ray tube current: 40 μA
X-ray source distance: 10 mm
Resolution of X-ray image: 3.4 μm

Stacked X-ray scan images

$$S(\mathbf{p}) = \int_{W(\mathbf{p})} S'(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}$$

where \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r} - three-dimensional vectors and $W(\mathbf{p})$ is the window of integration, $W(\mathbf{p}) : \forall \{x_1, x_2, x_3\} (|x_1 - p_1| \leq w_r, |x_2 - p_2| \leq w_r, |x_3 - p_3| \leq w_r)$. The vector \mathbf{p} defines a current position of the integration

Degree of anisotropy

$$\beta = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_3} & \text{if } \lambda_3 > 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } \lambda_3 = 0. \end{cases}$$

Structure tensor & "Voxel model" [1]

$$S'(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial x_1}\right)^2 & \frac{\partial I}{\partial x_1} \frac{\partial I}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial I}{\partial x_1} \frac{\partial I}{\partial x_3} \\ & \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial x_2}\right)^2 & \frac{\partial I}{\partial x_2} \frac{\partial I}{\partial x_3} \\ \text{sym} & & \left(\frac{\partial I}{\partial x_3}\right)^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

I : three-dimensional 8-bit gray values of CT images

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Micro-CT analysis of internal geometry of chopped carbon fiber tapes reinforced thermoplastics

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where λ_1 and λ_3 are lowest and highest eigenvalues of the structure tensor respectively.

Two-dimensional histogram combined in-plane orientation (φ_{XY}) and out-of-plane orientation (θ_{XY}) distribution in total volume (the color bar indicate data density)

Reconstructed 3D model

3D micro model with visualized Phi_XY (φ_{XY}) distribution (the color bar indicate φ_{XY} value)

CTT

Single VOI - C

Definition of Volume of Interest (VOI)

$$S(\mathbf{p}) = \int_{W(\mathbf{p})} S'(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}$$

Window size $W(\mathbf{p})$

Unfolded

Cross section

Unfolded histograms of φ_{XY} (a) and θ_{XY} (b)

0.7 mm

SM-CTT

BM-CTT

0.7 mm

FC-CTT

0.7 mm

SM-CTT

FC-CTT

BM-CTT

Effect of molding processes on in-plane orientation (φ_{XY})

SM-CTT

BM-CTT

FC-CTT

Effect of molding processes on in-plane orientation (φ_{XY})

SM-CTT

BM-CTT

FC-CTT

Effect of molding processes on in-plane orientation (φ_{XY})

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Effect of molding processes on in-plane orientation (φ_{XY})

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Effect of molding processes on out-of-plane orientation (θ_{XY})

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- Novel and reliable X-ray μ -CT analysis methodology based on VoxTex is given to analysis the internal geometries of CTT (one kind of ROS).
- Effects of molding processes on the internal geometry of CTT have been evaluated quantitatively and visually.
- SM-CTT show the most stable and regular internal geometry that tape morphology can be reproduced.
- BM-CTT have significant “tape sticking” and show the most serious out-of-plane orientation (θ_{XY}) disorder due to the bulking process during compression molding.
- FC-CTT show less θ_{XY} disorder but the taps show unimpregnated condition, also the internal geometry demonstrated critical “tape splitting” and almost no tape morphology can be observed.
- SM-CTT have stable and regular internal geometry not only show reproducible mechanical performance but also have better CAE capability, while the BM-CTT and FC-CTT with strong internal geometry irregularity show the limitation on applications.
- The X-ray μ -CT methodologies can provide useful information for ROS characterization with the consideration of molding processes in both material researches and industrial applications.

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